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#1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Guide

This guide is designed to help teachers, researchers, and developers understand the growing importance of integrating technology into educational practices, driven by its rapid evolution across various fields. It highlights the significant benefits technology brings to education, as teachers can see students develop and practice key skills to the learning process, enabling teachers to access data about the initial level of students, their motivation, behavior, and about the ways the acquired experience benefits them in the classroom, in acquiring information and adapting in the school setting. Students are the direct beneficiaries of innovative and effective educational tools. Technology products are essential for researchers as we need to better understand the pros and cons that technology brings, and building bridges between several domains is of great importance in advancing our knowledge about gamification, applications, serious games, usability, and how children and adults can benefit as much as possible. Developers built technology tools that scaffold advancements in several domains and integrate their knowledge with information from research, education, psychology, computer science, and ethics to build and use technology most beneficially for as many people (children and adults). The serious games that developers build integrate the feedback from neurodiverse children and their teachers, and the discussions between experts in several fields enrich the algorithms in the technology.

Each section of the guide includes examples drawn from the experience of developing the EMPOWER platform.

The EMPOWER platform uses Technology, Psychology, and Special Education to build a core educational platform that aims to engage neurodiverse children in serious games that assess and train key skills and strategies. As the needs of every child may be different, teachers, with their extensive experience and knowledge about the child, help children navigate the platform and exercise their minds in a personalized intervention.

In this document, we present EMPOWER, our novel digital platform with serious games designed to be user-friendly for children. The games are designed for neurodiverse children aged between 7 and 14 years old, who often present difficulties in cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and social domains and sometimes find their way in the learning processes with difficulty and need constant exercise and attention from teachers.

EMPOWER is based on research and new paradigms from Special Education, Psychology, and Technology that suggest and explain how executive functions and emotional regulation are key skills that need to be targeted in the educational intervention for neurodiverse students.

The core output of EMPOWER is thus an educational platform that facilitates the improvement of these key skills in neurodiverse children and that allows multiple repetitions of a game, which enhances, for example, sustained attention, and children become better with repetition. We know that games allow children to exercise the key abilities with ease, as games also use AI to self-adapt as children play.

1.2 Importance of Technology in Education

Technologies have advanced significantly during the last 10 years, influencing not only society but also education. Daily use of technology is a fact and has changed even the interaction between children and teachers and it has made possible for education to continue even in times of uncertainty or health distress (Wang et al., 2004). Although its use can be both detrimental and beneficial, we cannot deny that students have access to technology and spend a lot of time involved in apps, games, or social media. Our purpose is to support children in learning, making them better equipped for a rapidly changing society that requires agile adaptation, and neurodiverse children need tailored interventions and games.

Technology has a significant impact on education and psychology as it supports research, it enhances the learning experience, and widens the pathways in which psychological concepts are taught and understood (Krodinger et al., 2013; Riva & Wiederhold, 2020).

For example, technology offers excellent tools for assessing and developing a wide range of skills and abilities (Chai, Koh & Tsai, 2021). The Empower platform incorporates many of these advantages, focusing on education, psychological competencies, and research. One key feature is the use of gamification, which helps keep children engaged in the activities. Each skill we aim to assess and develop is carefully tailored

into a serious game, complete with various scenarios, avatars, stars, badges, and other elements that aim to maintain the child's interest (Sailer & Homner, 2020; Subhash & Cudney, 2018).

Additionally, the platform offers different levels of difficulty for each game, ensuring accessibility and promoting continuous progress for the target group. Another notable feature is the integration of various gadgets, such as an eye-tracker and a smart watch, to monitor the child's physical activity during platform testing. Finally, the teachers can easily track each child's progress in developing specific skills. Through the app, teachers can view performance data for each game and session. The app also provides personalized recommendations for the child, suggesting the most suitable game and difficulty level based on the child's performance, through algorithms.

1.3 Addressing the Needs of Neurodiverse Children

Addressing the needs of neurodiverse children requires an approach that assesses individual needs and integrates these in a holistic yet individualized intervention (Landa & Garrett-Mayer, 2006; Zeng & Liu, 2021). The conditions that are included under the NDD umbrella, autism spectrum disorder (ASD), attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), dyslexia, and intellectual disabilities, influence and many times affect behavior, social adaptation, child's development, including cognitive, emotional, social skills, learning, communication, and behavior. Providing a platform in which key skills are assessed and the intervention is tailored can help neurodiverse children thrive (Wiley & Bailey, 2021).

One of the needs of neurodiverse children is the early identification of disorders, but also identifying how each individual executive function functions or which emotion regulation strategy is employed usually provides essential information as a screening tool and as an assessment in the platform, and for an individualized treatment plan.

Neurodiverse children need individualized treatment plans to support their success in school, and teachers provide and foster information that best suits their needs. Teachers also adapt different types of support (Samiuddin, 2022).

Neurodiverse children often benefit from an Individualized Education Plan (IEP), which outlines specific goals, accommodations, and services needed for the child to succeed in an academic setting. Usually, IEPs

are personalized to address each child's strengths, challenges, and learning style, but including specific EF and emotional regulation strategies enhances the benefits of the plans by including essential assessments and progress.

Through the Empower platform, we aim to assess executive functions and emotional regulation, using the results to create a personalized IEP for each child. Using the Teacher App, teachers can easily track each child's progress. The app provides personalized recommendations for the child, suggesting the most suitable game and difficulty level based on the child's performance.

To ensure the platform, games, and overall setup were well-suited for neurodiverse children, we actively integrated their input, their teachers' feedback, and our observations from the pilot studies. This input was carefully considered and directly influenced the changes and ongoing development of the platform and various game elements.

1.4 How Technology Can Support Diverse Needs

By using technology, both children and teachers can access resources and use platforms with interactive learning tools that involve children in experiential learning. Technology allows children to learn at their own level of abilities and allows teachers and researchers to assess and adapt the content to best fit the needs of children. This characteristic is especially important as some skills need more repetitions for some children and technology fosters an environment where there is possible to engage in almost as many repetitions as the child wants without an extensive intervention from the teacher who may be present but only intervenes when necessary, this saving effort from the teacher's perspective and making the child feel that they invest little effort while exercising.

As the needs differ and change over time and data collection and analysis are both essential for research in psychology, special education, and technology advances in gathering data from the serious games and it may generate reports in which we could see how the child learns and adapts, in the EMPOWER platform AI is involved and children receive differentiated feedback. By using the EMPOWER, we aim to help teachers and children gain key skills, and we gather data that allows us to adapt the games to the best use for children.

Technology supports neurodiverse children and their special needs as the levels of the games allow children

to play the same game in a class, for example, but every child can reach a further level based on their performance and their current level of development. This aids education as technology finds a way to support and tailor needs at a very fast pace, with little intervention for teachers, so that they can direct their attention to processes that only they can perform.

The technology used in the EMPOWER platform assesses the current level of the child and provides a better understanding of their needs, thus, it may be viewed as a platform that provides psychological and educational support, accessible and friendly. In addition to providing user-friendly serious games, it provides a means of digital intervention as the skills are exercised many times, and children and teachers see the progress and its use in a school setting.

The EMPOWER platform has transformed recent psychology and special education research from executive function, emotional regulation, technology, usability domains, into serious games fit to be extensively exercised in an accessible manner that improves retention and training. Through gamification, the learning processes involved in training the skills found to be key components in neurodiverse children have become more interactive, enjoyable, and encouraging children to become more involved, and they may wish to engage in more repetition, which translates to more proactive for a key ability.

Involving eye-tracking, our platform could be an effective method for understanding cognitive load and how individuals process complex information, offering valuable insights into learning and how key executive skills function in neurodiverse children.

Using AI and machine learning algorithms to assess or predict mental health outcomes (Dunn et al., 2019) based on data from the games, self-reports, demographics, and behavioral patterns could allow us a better prediction of the development of neurodiverse children and identify the key areas where children need more attention. Our platform assists psychological assessment and can be used as a mean of prevention and intervention in detecting the skills that were thought to function optimally but still need attention and rehearsal.

Considering the importance of executive functions and emotion regulation in our interaction, we consider the use of technology in our advantage a support for children and teachers altogether.

Using technology and specifically designing serious games informed by research and the newest advancements in technology is one of the ways in which technology is put to better use in the EMPOWER platform.

Knowing that children need to be engaged and their need to behave as their peers and that most children spend a lot of time playing games, building games that foster sustained attention, memory, being able to calm intense emotions and adapt to situations that seem to be unfair are some of the ways in which our platform helps advance both the use of technology and education by engaging students in games that enrich their education.

The EMPOWER platform engages neurodiverse children in several games that are designed based on two concepts: Executive Functions (EFs) and Emotion Regulation (ER) strategies. The fully interactive and gamified application keeps the child completely engaged while the game is measuring and getting data about their performance, to feed the algorithms developed and to create a personalized intervention and self-adaption in the games.

The EMPOWER platform also uses eye tracking and wearables, as they enable data collection that contributes to developing interactive games for neurodiverse children, aiming to reduce emotional and behavioral challenges. Wearable devices are increasingly utilized to monitor and support individuals with neurodiverse conditions; however, considerations such as sensory processing issues, behavioral regulation, and cognitive challenges necessitate careful implementation (Meijer et al., 2018). Stasolla (2021) critically examines the use of virtual reality and wearable technologies to enhance adaptive responses in neurodiverse children and adolescents. Zheng and Wang (2023) explore the use of wearable devices in clinical research for neurological and psychiatric diagnosis and monitoring. This study highlights the advancements in sensor technology, data processing, and machine learning that enhance the accuracy of wearable-based assessments, but there are some challenges related to data reliability and privacy concerns.

The researchers underline the potential of these devices in real-time monitoring, early detection of disorders, and as a part of a personalized intervention for patients, but we need to take into consideration the size of the wearables and children's attitudes towards them.

WP2 focuses on defining games based on Executive Functions (EFs) and Emotion Regulation (ER) strategies for integration into the final platform. WP3 involves developing a fully interactive, gamified application that engages children while tracking their performance. The collected data will inform WP4, refining algorithms for personalized interventions and adaptive gameplay. This deliverable highlights the platform's essential features supporting the games from WP2. In WP 6, the platform is tested in several pilot studies, one validation study, and one randomized clinical study.

1.5 EMPOWER Game Platform - Theoretical background and examples

Our primary goal in developing this serious-game-based platform was to empower teachers with the tools and knowledge necessary to effectively support neurodiverse children in school (Barkey, 1997). By addressing these difficulties that children usually encounter, our aim was and is to enhance the overall well-being and quality of life of these children, enabling them to thrive both academically and personally (Ren et al., 2023). The platform features a diverse selection of interactive games and activities specifically designed for neurodiverse children. These activities are serving a dual purpose: first, to assess various cognitive, emotional, and behavioral skills (Kollins et al., 2021), and second, to provide targeted training to strengthen the skills necessary for success in school and daily life (Ramos & Garcia, 2019). By incorporating engaging and evidence-based gameplay, the platform fosters an environment where children can develop essential abilities in a fun and motivating way.

A key innovation of the EMPOWER platform is its structured two-phase approach, consisting of both an evaluation and an intervention phase. The evaluation phase provides a comprehensive profile of a child's executive functioning (Miyake et al, 2000) and emotional regulation, identifying strengths as well as specific areas that require further development. This initial assessment enables teachers and caregivers to gain valuable insights into the child's needs and tailor their support accordingly.

Following the assessment, the intervention phase is designed to actively enhance the child's underdeveloped skills through targeted exercises and training programs. By engaging with the platform, children can practice and refine critical abilities such as impulse control, working memory, cognitive flexibility, and emotional self-regulation. The interactive nature of the platform ensures that learning

remains engaging and adaptive to each child's progress.

To further support both educators and students, the platform is equipped with a robust data collection system and an internal report generator. These features enable the continuous tracking of student progress, allowing teachers to monitor improvements over time and set personalized objectives for each child. This data-driven approach ensures that interventions remain effective and adaptable to the child's evolving needs.

Additionally, the project includes dedicated training sessions for teachers, ensuring they are well-equipped to implement the platform effectively within the classroom. We offer a series of teacher training modules delivered through interactive presentations. Each module provides a detailed overview of the games, explaining their intended educational objectives and the specific competencies they aim to develop. The training also includes a set of indicators to help teachers identify potential areas where students may struggle. Additionally, the modules present the standardized tasks each game is based on (e.g., the Corsi Blocks Task by Milner, 1971, for the working memory game). Finally, the training goes further into the purpose and mechanics of each game to ensure a comprehensive understanding. By providing educators with specialized knowledge and practical guidance, we aim to maximize the impact of the platform and ensure a consistent, well-informed approach to supporting neurodiverse children.

Through this comprehensive and innovative platform, we seek to bridge the gap between assessment and intervention, offering teachers a valuable tool to foster the cognitive, emotional, and social development of children in need.

Cognitive training through serious games can be highly beneficial for neurodiverse children by targeting areas such as attention, memory, executive function, and self-regulation.

These tasks serve as the foundation for the games, and the way children perform on them provides the data needed for the algorithms. The algorithms are capable of supplying the teachers with information that allows them to adjust the level of their games to the students' performance. Additionally, the algorithms provide feedback in a suitable format to all relevant stakeholders of EMPOWER, including teachers, students, and parents.

Executive functioning encompasses a group of advanced cognitive processes that support goal-directed actions and help individuals navigate new or unfamiliar situations (Diamond, 2020).

For example, in the working memory task, the child is to pick up the yellow peppers as they ripe while considering the order, and they receive feedback. This task is research-based (Milner, 1971), and it requires the child to keep in mind the position of the peppers as well as sorting them following a criterion (with or without a worm). The score of this task highlights how many peppers the child has selected correctly, in the exact order that they appeared.

#2. Recommendations

2.1 Recommendations for developing technologies for neurodiverse children

Developing technologies for neurodiverse children needs to take into consideration their unique cognitive, emotional, and behavioral needs. Neurodiverse children can benefit from many technologies, such as applications, games, sensor technologies, and virtual reality, in supporting behavioral and emotional regulation (López & Morales, 2020). The negative part of research regarding technologies and neurodiverse children is that most games remain at the prototyping stage and lack further implementation and testing. One of the first recommendations regards the need for further development and testing. The second recommendation is to reassess children's needs and teachers' needs so that the feedback we receive is integrated into the technologies.

When developing technologies for neurodiverse children, an integrative approach is essential, requiring collaboration among specialists from various fields to ensure the creation of a technology that meets all the unique needs of these children and delivers the intended benefits.

The development of the Empower platform involved experts from research, psychology, special education, computer science, technology, and ethics. Each group contributed their expertise to create a comprehensive platform: from the foundational theories and research in psychology and special education, to the design

of engaging, functional games with an intuitive interface and seamless connectivity across devices (such as eye-tracking, smartwatches, and tablets). Additionally, thoughtful algorithms were developed to provide personalized recommendations for teachers using the platform. The final result is a well-functioning platform that integrates psychological and special education principles into a user-friendly product, all while adhering to ethical guidelines.

Serious games, designed to foster educational outcomes and provide information to players, have the potential to engage children while teaching them self-regulation skills. Cibrian, Lakes, Schuck and Hayes (2022) review of the literature revealed that serious games were delivered through various platforms, including mobile technology (22%), personal computers (22%), sensors (22%), and robots (11%) and easily accessible serious games should be considered.

From configuring the Empower games, we must note some key recommendations, particularly regarding serious games. First, the interface needs to be highly intuitive and easily accessible across various devices, whether through a touchscreen, keyboard, or mouse. The design should be simple yet vibrant, with recognizable elements. For example, we developed an eco-farm scenario with a map where each location represents a different game.

The design includes elements like forests, mushrooms, a barn, various vegetables, fruits, flowers, bees, and even waste. For the emotion-based games, we created a separate scenario within the farm—the farm fair—featuring specific fair activities like a big spinning wheel, corn-hole game, and an egg pyramid. Next, instructions must be simple and clear. For neurodiverse children who may struggle with reading, recorded instructions are a helpful tool to make the games more accessible. Finally, the games must strike a balance: they should be simple enough for children with more significant challenges to understand and engage with, yet complex enough to help them develop the skills we aim to enhance.

Based on the feedback we received from students and teachers, as well as our observations during the pilot sessions, we made several improvements to the games, specifically in terms of color schemes, gameplay dynamics, and instructional content. For instance, we increased the color variation to make the visuals more engaging and adjusted certain game dynamics: simplifying elements that were too challenging for our target audience and increasing the difficulty where the gameplay felt too easy. We also added more hints to guide

children through the games, even though each game already included a demo version. Additionally, we shortened the written instructions to make them more accessible and included audio recordings of the instructions to support children who are not yet able to read.

The EMPOWER gaming platform leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance student performance and well-being by processing real-time data from eye-tracking, wearable devices, and student performance. AI algorithms analyze this data to provide continuous feedback, enabling the game to self-adjust for better engagement and learning outcomes. Machine Learning (ML) predicts future performance and identifies strengths and weaknesses in executive functions and emotional regulation. These AI-driven insights directly influence game adaptation and feedback mechanisms and provide individualized feedback for neurodiverse children.

The EMPOWER gaming platform is the product of a multidisciplinary team, in which the feedback allows us to draw conclusions and discuss possible implications of the game, and having several perspectives and collaboration allows us to engage in choosing better feedback for children and teachers. For example, after every level, the child is congratulated so that they know that the game is finished, and the number of correct and incorrect answers is shown. After every game, the child receives a badge and stars that can be used in playing other games. The book of badges indicated the overall percentage of correct answers. Teachers also receive feedback regarding the progress of the assessment or the intervention, and at the end of a session, teachers are asked to answer a short questionnaire about the difficulties or other aspects of the game that can be changed.

2.2 Recommendations for the use of technology by teachers

Unlike gamification, which applies game-like elements to educational processes without creating full-fledged games, serious games are built around a structured narrative and a digital or physical environment designed specifically for learning (Scherer, Siddiq, & Sánchez Viveros, 2022). When integrating serious games into the classroom, teachers play a crucial role in maximizing their educational potential.

Here are some key recommendations for teachers to effectively use technology in serious games:

- Teachers should ensure that serious games are aligned with specific learning objectives and strengthen the connection between the games and the learning process, at an individual level. They need to be involved in the co-design of the games as part of the development team. During our pilot studies, we gathered feedback from teachers on several key aspects of the platform: how easily children could navigate it, their level of engagement with both the platform and the games, whether the instructions were clear and understandable, whether the response time allowed was sufficient, and if the difficulty levels were appropriate for their students. Teachers also commented on the overall appeal of the games and whether more personalization was needed. Based on their input, we implemented a range of improvements to make the platform more accessible and better suited to their students' needs.
- Teachers can better understand students' performance and perseverance, and engagement as the built-in analytics within the game monitors students' performance and identifies areas where they may need additional support. The Empower platform includes the Teachers App that provides personalized recommendations based on students' performance in the games. These recommendations are generated by algorithms that analyze the students' progress on the platform. However, the final decision regarding the next steps in the student's intervention rests with the teacher. In other words, while the app offers suggestions, the teacher has the flexibility to either follow those recommendations or adjust based on their observations of the student's performance, perseverance, and engagement.
- Providing feedback related to children's progress, teachers' encouragement to persevere, reinforce learning, and encourage improvement. Meanwhile, the children receive their own feedback directly on the screen of the tablet or laptop they're using, both during and after each game. The feedback provided to students is designed to be engaging and motivating, featuring stars, badges, points, and clues for the game, while teachers have access to more detailed statistics about their students' performance. This distinction ensures that feedback is appropriate for each audience—simpler and more rewarding for children, and more comprehensive and analytical for teachers. The goal is to empower teachers to make well-informed decisions regarding their students' training and next steps.
- Teachers need to be able to attend easy trainings during which they learn to navigate through the platform. They could design new interventions based on the knowledge obtained from their interaction with

the child and from the platform, as AI and machine learning algorithms provide additional and valuable information for the learning process and the game development. Teachers need to follow a training and then, when they use the platform, they follow several simple steps that guide them through the EMPOWER platform. Our recommendation is to reach out to teachers in a simple way so they can create new interventions and feel that it is easy to interact with the technology. One of the benefits of interacting with technology is the platform's analytics that can alert teachers whether the game is complete or there are interruptions, or frequent errors. Teachers decide about the intervention, and their decision can be based on the algorithm or not. After the initial evaluation, teachers can program an intervention for each student, and they have a map of the student's timetables and their progress.

2.3 Recommendations on the characteristics of the beneficiaries

Serious games stand out by seamlessly combining enjoyment with a clear educational purpose, adopting various formats. Designed to foster skill development, these games provide fun, entertainment, and emotional engagement while prioritizing learning as their main objective (Marsh & McKenna, 2017). When designing serious games for children aged 7-14, it is essential to consider their cognitive, emotional, and social development. Designing a simple yet interesting social and cognitive context is key to developing the games. In creating the Empower games, we chose the eco-farm scenario.

To maintain children's motivation and enjoyment, the development of new technology should incorporate fun elements, storytelling, and opportunities for exploration. In the Empower games, we've integrated various elements designed to keep children engaged. The game is set on an eco-farm where players can choose an avatar to represent themselves within this farming context. From the start, a farmer, acting as a social guide, accompanies the player throughout their journey, providing context and instructions for each game. Students have the freedom to explore the platform and decide which game to play. They can also access intuitive menus where they can view the badges they've collected during gameplay. Focusing on the emotion games, we've carefully designed scenarios within the farm fair context.

Each scenario is meant to evoke different emotions, allowing players to identify how they feel and reflect

on why they feel that way. Afterward, players are presented with a list of emotion regulation strategies and can select the one they believe is most suitable for their situation. This decision-making process empowers children, fostering a sense of control and promoting deeper engagement. Offering positive reinforcement by using badges, scores, and constructive feedback is one way to foster continuous motivation and support learning. In addition, we've incorporated several mini-games into the platform, strategically placed in areas where they would be most effective.

For example, BeeHold, the delay of gratification game, uses the mini game as both a gameplay element and a reward. Similarly, in the emotion games, mini-games are included to enhance interactivity and help children return to a baseline state after experiencing a range of emotions. Serious games should incorporate features that help children recognize and regulate their emotions, particularly for neurodiverse children, as these help them engage more with their executive functions at their best (Aksakal & Güven, 2020).

Implementing a gradual increase in challenge to match the child's learning curve and avoid frustration is also important (Miller & Williams, 2021). An essential feature of the Empower platform is that each game includes multiple levels of difficulty to ensure an appropriate progression. For the emotion games, there are two levels of difficulty, while for the executive function games, there are three.

The first level, serving as the entry point, should be simple enough to engage all users, while the subsequent levels gradually increase in difficulty to promote the development of targeted skills. For example, in the game Worm, which trains working memory, children must remember the position of peppers that change color from green to yellow. In the first level, children only need to remember the position of two peppers. In the second level, the number increases to three peppers, and in the third level, the challenge escalates further to four peppers.

This gradual increase of difficulty helps ensure the game remains both engaging and challenging, supporting the child's skill development at an appropriate pace.

Several adjustments were made to the levels of difficulty based on observations during the pilots and feedback from both teachers and students. These changes aimed to ensure the games were accessible to the target audience while also maintaining engagement by providing a clear progression in challenge.

Depending on the game and level, the adjustments either made tasks easier or introduced more complexity. For example, in the game ReStroop, a time limit was added starting from level 2, with an even shorter limit at level 3 to increase difficulty. In ReFlex, the number of trials was slightly reduced to help maintain focus and minimize frustration, and we introduced hint notes to help students recognize when the game rule had changed, supporting both understanding and reduced frustration levels.

2.4. Recommendations for researchers

Integrating technology into serious games research should be based on relevant and recent literature, and unfortunately, most studies that involve technology design test the games for only a limited amount of time. Considering our experience, we recommend:

1. Collaboration among experts from diverse fields, such as special education, psychology, game design, computer science, and business, to develop well-rounded and impactful serious games, and this collaboration should also encourage feedback from different fields, as this makes the games more complex. The serious games that are included in the EMPOWER platform are based on research and collaboration between different domains orients the researchers towards maximizing educational effectiveness and engagement, and include feedback from all the members of the team.
2. Including learning analytics to track and evaluate student interactions within the game, helping to pinpoint challenges and guide adjustments to the game design or instructional methods (Daoudi, 2022).
3. Prioritizing user-centered design is a key recommendation, as considering preferences, needs, and social interactions enhances both engagement and effectiveness. Meaningful social interaction within the game can greatly enrich the learning experience, encouraging repeated play as an enjoyable activity rather than a demanding school task.
4. Using an iterative design approach is crucial when developing a game, particularly when the target beneficiaries are neurodiverse children, to ensure that we effectively meet their needs. During the development of the Empower platform, we conducted three pilot studies, gathering feedback from both teachers and students. Based on their input and our observations during the pilots, we made several adjustments. For instance, we introduced a child-friendly calibration app for the eye tracker, came with a standardized setting with minimal requirements, increased the complexity of the sustained attention game, and extended the wait time and reward level (including a mini-game) for the delay of gratification game. These examples highlight the importance of continuous testing and refinement, ensuring that the

technology aligns with its intended purpose and effectively meets the needs of the beneficiaries.

5. Finally, when several types of technologies and devices are used, it is important that they are tested together to ensure good integration, to be able to fix possible bugs early on, and to test their performance together.

The EMPOWER platform uses iterative design, a design that involves continuously refining and improving the product through the cycles of developing, testing, receiving feedback, and then making the necessary adjustments. Our games went through several changes, and in the context of neurodiverse children, iterative design is essential in optimizing usability, engagement, and maximizing learning outcomes. Our platform incorporates multiple design, testing, and feedback cycles from children, teachers, and experts in psychology, special education, and technology, and three pilot studies led us to consider changes in the game.

The EMPOWER platform integrates AI and Machine Learning (ML), wearable devices, and student performance. This allows serious games to provide feedback, self-adjust to individual needs, and offer personalized interventions for neurodiverse children. The EMPOWER platform is constantly evolving through collaboration between experts from different fields, ensuring that its research-based games are not just engaging and accessible but also genuinely helpful in supporting children's cognitive and emotional growth. The EMPOWER platform uses an integration process that ensures the technologies are collected in a synchronized process, properly. It also tests everything at once to make sure the games function at an optimal level. The design focuses on the user, with regular testing and improvements to keep the games engaging and effective.

3. Conclusion and Future Trends

Technologies must be user-friendly and incorporate key elements such as concentration, clear objectives, feedback, challenge, autonomy, immersion, social interaction, and knowledge enhancement. Serious games allow participants to test strategies and learn from mistakes, and refine their approach without facing real-world consequences.

Developing technologies for neurodiverse children needs to attend to their unique cognitive, emotional, and behavioral needs, and integrating research and technology can bring these children great benefits. However, many technologies remain in the prototype stage without extensive implementation and testing, and unfortunately, they are not tested for more than a few years.

The development of the EMPOWER platform highlights the importance of an integrative approach, combining expertise from psychology, special education, technology, computer science, and ethics. We recommend that future research teams consider multidisciplinary meetings and feedback, building engaging, user-friendly designs, and enabling continuous feedback and self-adjustment to tailor interventions to individual needs. This collaboration ensures that the platform meets the diverse needs of neurodiverse children while delivering tangible benefits. The platform's serious games are designed to be intuitive and accessible, with engaging, research-based content such as eco-farm scenarios and emotion-based activities like the farm fair.

It is recommended to include AI and Machine Learning in developing platforms for neurodiverse children, as these allow real-time data analysis, personalized interventions, and continuous feedback. Additionally, incorporating reward systems and asking and integrating insights from teachers, as well as providing feedback for teachers to adjust the intervention, can enhance engagement and support cognitive and emotional development.

In conclusion, unlike gamification, which integrates game-like elements into educational processes, serious games are designed with a structured narrative, based on research and multiple field collaboration. Teachers

play a critical role in maximizing the educational potential of serious games by aligning them with learning objectives, monitoring student performance, and designing interventions that take into consideration the data that has already been collected.

3.1 Evolving Role of Technology in Education

Technology has greatly impacted special education, psychology, and education by improving communication across various fields, personalizing learning experiences, and addressing diverse learning needs. Its integration into education has led educational psychology to evolve, embracing multidisciplinary strategies and emphasizing the development of skills needed to better adapt in fast fast-paced changing society. Digital tools now play a key role in fostering constructivist learning environments.

The future of technology in education should revolve around creating accessible applications with intuitive, specific, and clear instructions tailored to each technology's unique features. These advancements should not only focus on individual users but must also prioritize integration between different stakeholders—parents, students, and teachers—allowing for a more seamless and collaborative learning experience.

Furthermore, technology in education should be seen as part of an ongoing process of development, continuously evolving to meet the needs of diverse learning environments and to stay responsive to emerging trends and challenges in the educational field.

3.1 Empowering Educators to Integrate Technology Effectively

Integrating technology into serious games research requires a strong foundation in relevant, recent literature, as many studies only test games for short periods. Based on our experience, we highly recommend collaboration among diverse experts — special education, psychology, education, game design, computer science, and business. A second recommendation involves using the analytics provided by games to adjust both the game itself and the interventions. We also suggest considering individualized interventions and employing a user-centered design that focuses on preferences, needs, and social interactions to enhance engagement, effectiveness, and enjoyment.

The iterative design approach is crucial in developing a platform that effectively meets the needs of neurodiverse children. Since the EMPOWER platform incorporates wearables, we recommend utilizing off-the-shelf technologies and integrating these devices to ensure multiple means of collecting data.

Considering the comprehensive review of games, Baranowski et al. (2016) summarize the topics of games used in interventions: with 33% aimed at supporting children with school-related activities. Only 11% were designed for use at home or in a clinic, while the rest were either tested in a lab setting or lacked a specific location for use. Most of the research focused primarily on the design and development process (88%), though some empirical studies included lab (33%), deployment (11%), or case (11%) studies.

To empower teachers and immerse them in technology as a tool for education, it is essential to consider the diverse range of subjects taught in schools, ensuring that tools and resources are tailored to meet the specific needs of each discipline. Targeted training programs are essential in helping educators effectively integrate these technologies into their teaching practices. Moreover, the development of a joint online platform across Europe could create a centralized hub for resources, fostering collaboration and providing easy access to educational materials.

Finally, technologies designed for educational purposes should undergo an ongoing process of development, continuously adapting to the evolving educational environment and enhancing accessibility and the quality of learning, especially in light of the rapid advancements in technology.

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